

Interview on urban freight delivery and loading spaces

Dear planner/transport engineer,

My name is Quan (Jack) Yuan, a postdoc research associate from the Department of City and Regional Planning, the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill. I am working with the department chair Dr. Noreen McDonald on a research project about the provision of on-street and off-street loading spaces in major cities in the North Carolina and beyond. We would like to know how local departments of planning and transportation have been dealing with the increased demand for urban deliveries and providing on-street and off-street loading zones to accommodate the demand. This information hopefully can help planners and engineers better allocate on-street curb space and off-street land to serve the needs of different transportation modes, mitigate multi-modal conflicts, and improve the efficiency of urban freight deliveries.

To collect the data, we are getting in touch with urban planners and transport engineers who are familiar with this issue and recruiting interviewees to participate in the conversation. We suppose you may be familiar with practices and policies related to the freight planning and curb space allocation, according to your title at the department of planning/transportation. We really appreciate that your offer of participating in this interview and your contribution to our research. If you know someone else in your city who is also experienced in freight planning or interested in discussing the topic, please let us know or directly forward this interview questionnaire to him/her. We are indeed thankful for all your kind help!

Screening:

1. Are you familiar with urban freight planning/engineering, in particular on/off-street loading spaces?
Yes—(continue)
No—is there someone else in your department that I should speak with about this study? If yes, please provide contact information below

[if Yes] Thanks so much. The interview should take about no more than **30 minutes**. If you do not have answers to certain questions, please just leave it blank. Now, let's get started!

2. What is your **job title**?
3. What are your major **responsibilities**?
4. Is **urban freight delivery** an issue in your community? For instance, in terms of blocking the traffic and causing congestion? Any complaints or difficulties related to this issue?
5. Which parts of the city do you think suffer from the most serious urban **freight delivery difficulties**?
6. Do you have **minimum off-street loading requirements** in the municipal zoning codes? Do you know when the requirements were updated last time?

7. Do you have any specific requirements for the **provision of on-street loading spaces** in the codes? How does the city regulate such provision?

8. Is there a comprehensive scheme or approach for **allocating on-street loading spaces**? For instance, do local businesses or residential apartments participate in the allocation of on-street loading spaces?

9. Does the city witness many **violations** of loading space use regulations? For instance, on-street loading spaces are occupied by passenger vehicles or other items. Are the violations recorded? Is their information associated with the citations about location, time of day, type of vehicle, etc.? Is the information used for planning purposes?

10. Does the city encounter these difficulties when **enforcing the rules** of using on-street loading spaces?
 - On-street loading spaces are occupied by non-freight vehicles or objects
 - The time length of on-street loading space exceeds the maximum length
 - The size or type of vehicles does not conform with regulations
 - Others, please name it.

11. How does the city cope with the difficulties and improve the efficiency of loading space use? Any recent measures for addressing the freight delivery problem?

12. Do you have anything else to share with us about this topic? We really appreciate your time and help.